

Perception and Awareness of Artificial Intelligence Tools among Science Teachers in Gashu'a Education Zone, Yobe-Nigeria

Mohammed Umar,²Abubakar Imam Isa,³Haruna Hajarat Ozozoma,⁴Idris Abdullahi &
⁵Adamu Adamu

Department of Science and Technology Education, Bayero University, Kano Nigeria

²Department of Integrated Science, College of Education and Legal Studies Nguru, Yobe State.

³Department of Science Education, Confluence University of Science and Technology Osara, Kogi State

⁴Police Children School Kutigi, Niger State

⁵Department of Biology, Umar Suleiman College of Education, Gashu'a Yobe State

mohdumarhura@gmail.com, Tel: +23492836264

This study assessed the perception and awareness of senior secondary school science teachers towards artificial intelligence tool in Gashu'a Education Zone Yobe-Nigeria. The study was based on Naturalistic Theory of Perception. This study used a descriptive survey design. The study's population included 289 senior secondary school science teachers in Gashu'a Education Zone. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 162 senior secondary school science teachers. The data collection instrument was designated as the Artificial Intelligence Tool Perception and Awareness Questionnaire (AITPAQ) and was validated by experts and pilot tested with 25 teachers. The reliability coefficient of 0.72 obtained using Cronbach's alpha through the split half method. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and null hypotheses were tested using an independent sample t-test at 0.05 levels of significance using Statistical Package for Social Science version 23.0. The findings of the study demonstrated that science teachers exhibited AI tool awareness but had a negative perception about AI tool. Therefore, it was recommended that government organize training programs to develop science teachers' perceptions of AI tool.

Keywords
Perception,
Awareness,
Artificial
Intelligence
Tool, Gender,
Science
Teachers.

Introduction

The era of 4th industrial revolution thrives in the midst of rapid technological advancement where AI is one of the innovations shaping the daily lives of people (Safar, 2024). The adoption of AI in teaching learning has revolutionized instructional presentation providing interactive learning experience (Haque, 2024). AI is a computer-based imitation of human intelligence, programmed in such a way to think, learn and execute orders that usually require human intellect (Rehman, Riaz, Kausar, & Akram, 2025). AI plays a critical role in assisting instructors

with tool to create unique curricula that help develop individual skills and learning achievement for students considering students' weaknesses, interests and strengths (Alsharidah & Alkramiti, 2024). AI is often associated with time saving, increasing teachers' motivation, encouraging creativity, providing immediate feedback, cost efficiency and building self confidence among teachers. Despite these numerous benefits, AI is often associated with flaws, including the potential to foster laziness, inadequate access to technology reduce human interaction and increases inequality and potential for job loss (Paie,2025; Asgap

& Khatima, 2024; Uretmen, 2024). Notable AI tool in educational setting encompass virtual reality automated grading system, gamification, catboats, virtual assistance (Fakhar et al., 2024).

AI tool are applied in numerous educational scenarios including personalized intelligent teaching, remote education, school administration, student assessment and grading- test item generation, test interpretation , test scoring and grading (Chen et al. 2020; Owan, et al., 2023). Considering the worthwhile nature of this innovation, there is the need to assess teachers' awareness and perception as teachers are vested with the responsibility of actual implementation of the curriculum. Perception involves the active process of interpreting sensory information in order to construct a meaningful representation of one's environment. It involves both neural processing of external stimuli and cognitive influences such as attention, memory and expectation influenced by cultural upbringing, past experiences, social influences and individual differences (Pandy & Angadi, 2024; Chen & Whitney, 209). Awareness on the other hand entails the ability to conceptualize the available AI technology resources as well as how they can be used to fulfill academic responsibilities (Thomas et al., 2024).

The study is based on Naturalistic Theory of Perception by the senses Dewey, 925. The naturalistic theory of perception argues that our ability to perceive and make sense of the world is not a camera-like recording of data. Instead, it is an active, purposeful and embodied process shaped by our evolutionary history, our immediate need and goals in our environment. The most fascinating scope in which this theory relates to the present study is that teachers perceive

AI through the lenses of action and goals- teachers' primary goals are to educate, manage classrooms, assess students' learning and foster development, their perception of AI will be filtered through these goals. They will perceive AI not as abstract technology, but in terms of what it affords them in their professional development, for example, a teacher might perceive an AI grading tool as affording "time saving." These variables were examined in relation to sex. Gender refers to the socially constructed roles, expectations, and identities that a given society considers appropriate for women and men (Hyde et al., 209).

There is substantial literature with reference to teachers' perception and awareness both in the global and local contexts, For example, in a study carried out by Lawal (2025) on the assessment and implementation of artificial intelligence tool in biology teaching and learning at secondary schools in Ilorin, Nigeria, the outcome of the study showed that there was no significant difference in the perception toward AI between male and female teachers. Moreover, in study carried out by Ezekiel and Akinyemi (2022) on the utilization of artificial intelligence in education: the perception of the university of Ibadan lecturers, the result of the study showed that there was no significant difference in the perception of the lecturers on the basis of gender. Additionally, Pandey (2024) conducted a study on teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards AI in school education: gender perspective, the results of the study demonstrated that there was a significant disparity in the perception between male and female teachers. Furthermore, in the study conducted by Guneyli, et al. (2024) titled exploring teachers' awareness of artificial intelligence in educate teachers' study from northern Cyprus, the outcome of the study

demonstrated that the discrepancy in the awareness of male and female teachers was insignificant. Also, in the study conducted by Nyaaba et al. (2024) on generative AI in academic research: a descriptive study on awareness, gender usage and views among pre-service teachers, the result of the study revealed that male pre-service teachers have higher awareness towards AI than female pre-service teachers. Moreover, in study conducted by Okafor, and Anyanwu (2025) on teachers' awareness and utilization of artificial intelligence tool for curriculum implementation in secondary schools in the Anambra state, the outcome of the study showed that there was no significant difference in the awareness of male and female teachers towards artificial intelligence.

Statement of the Problem

A substantial number of studies have researched the efficacy of AI in teaching, learning and education in general. However, despite the significant roles of AI, secondary school science teachers tend not to utilize technology in their routine based on practical experience. The full benefits of this technology cannot be realized unless educators are aware of its importance and ability to use it effectively (Safar, 2024). This situation may be caused by several factors, such as lack of awareness about modern inventions and negative perception about AI invention. The study revealed that the utilization of AI from the perspective of teachers draws attention to the fact that the use of AI may differ in practice of teachers from different fields and gender should also be taken in to consideration (Kalnina, et al., 2024), additionally, limited literature exists in relation to secondary school science teachers' perception and awareness more importantly in Gashu' a Education Zone, and this created a gap that needs to be explored; hence, the need to carry

out the study on the AI tool perception and awareness of secondary school science teachers In Gashu'a Education Zone to provide valuable insight for policy makers.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the differences in the AI tool perception of male and female secondary school science teachers in the Gashu'a Education Zone.
2. To examine the differences in the AI tool awareness among male and female secondary school science teachers in the Gashu'a Education Zone.

Research Questions

1. To what extent do male and female secondary school science teachers in Gashu'a Education Zone differ in AI tool perception?
2. To what extent do male and female secondary school science teachers in Gashu'a Education Zone differ in AI tool awareness?

Research Hypotheses

- H₀:** There is no significant difference in the AI tool perception of male and female secondary school science teachers in the Gashu'a Education Zone.
- H₀₂** There is no significant difference in AI tool awareness among male and female secondary school science teachers in the Gashu'a Education Zone.

Methodology

This study was conducted with population of senior secondary school science teachers. The study was designed as descriptive survey. The study was based on Naturalistic Theory of Perception. The population of the study comprised of 289 senior secondary science teachers in Gashu'a education zone. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 62 science teachers. Artificial Intelligence Tool

Perception and Awareness Questionnaire (AITPAQ) was the instrument for data collection. It was adapted and modified from Haque (2024); Alraimi, et al. (2024), Uretmen (2024) and Ndidi (2024). The questionnaire was divided in to three sections (Section A, B & C), Section A consisted of Students’ demographic data, B and C assessed the perception and awareness of teachers towards AI tool respectively. The questionnaire was based on 5 point- Likert scale Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree with their corresponding points of ,2,3,4 and 5 respectively. Scores ranging from 2.49 from below was considered negative while scores of 2.5 and above were considered positive on

the perception and awareness scale. The collected data were ordinal scale data.

The instrument was validated by experts and pilot tested with 25 teachers who were part of the population but not in the sample. A reliability coefficient of 0.72 was obtained using Cronbach’s alpha through the split half method. The primary justification for the use of simple random sampling was its ability to generate an unbiased representative sample that allows for valid statistical generalization about the secondary school science teachers. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and the corresponding null hypotheses were tested using an independent sample t-test at a significance level of 0.05

Results

Table :Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of the Perception of Male and Female Science Teachers

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference
Male	90	.9	0.6	0.2
Female	72	.7	0.5	

As shown in Table above, the mean perception score and standard deviation of male science teachers were .9 and 0.6 and for female science teachers was .7 and 0.5 respectively with a mean difference of 0.2 in favor of male science teachers.

HO: There is no significant difference in the AI tool perception of male and female secondary school science teachers in the Gashu’a Education Zone.

Table 2:Independent Sample t-tests Analysis on the AI tool perception of male and Female Secondary school Science Teachers in Gashu’a Education Zone:

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p-value	Mean Difference	95%CI	Remark
Male	90	.9	0.6	.45	60	0.49	0.20	-0.07, 0.47	Not Sigt.
Female	72	.7	0.5						

From Table 2 above, the observed p-value was 0.49 which is greater than the significance level of 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, there was no significant difference in the perceptions of male and female science teachers about AI tool.

Research Question 2:

To what extent do male and female secondary school science teachers in the Gashu’a Education Zone differ in AI tool awareness?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of the AI tool Awareness of Male and Female Science Teachers

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference
Male	90	2.80	0.35	0.3
Female	72	2.77	0.32	

As shown in Table 3, the mean awareness score and standard deviation of male science teachers were 2.80 and 0.35 and of female science teachers were 2.77 and 0.32 respectively with a mean difference of 0.30 in favor of male science teachers.

HO₂ There is no significant difference in AI tool awareness among male and female secondary school science teachers in the Gashu’a Education Zone.

Table 4:Independent Sample t-tests Analysis on the AI tool Awareness of male and Female Science Teachers in Gashu’a Education Zone.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value	Mean Difference	95%CI	Remark
Male	90	2.80	0.35	0.56	60	0.575	0.30	0.32, 0.9	Not Significant.
Female	72	2.77	0.32						

From table 4, the observed p-value was 0.575 which is greater than the significance level of 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, there was no significant difference in the awareness of male and female science teachers about AI tool.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the findings of the study, it was found that a discrepancy in the mean perception scores was observed, with male science teachers demonstrating a higher average than female science teachers, it was further observed that there was no significant difference in the perception of male and female science teachers towards AI tool in education. The finding of this study is in agreement with the finding of Lawal (2025) who carried out study on the assessment and implementation of artificial intelligence tool

in Biology teaching and learning at secondary schools in Ilorin, Nigeria and found that there was no significant difference in the perception between male and female teachers towards AI and Ezekiel and Akinyemi (2022) who conducted a study on the utilization of artificial intelligence in education: the perception of university of Ibadan lecturers and found that there was no significant difference in the perception of the lecturers on the basis of gender. The study is contrary to the findings of Pandy (2024) who carried out a study on teachers’ perception and attitude towards AI in school education: gender perspective and found that there was a notable disparity in the perception between male and female teachers.

The result of this analysis also categorically unveiled a higher mean awareness score among male science

teachers relative to female science teachers; it further demonstrated that the discrepancy in the awareness of male and female science teachers was insignificant. The finding is in accordance with the findings of Guneyli et al. (2024); Okafor & Anyanwu, (2025) who found that there was no remarkable disparity in the awareness of male and female science teachers towards artificial intelligence in education. The finding is contrary to the finding of Nyaaba et al. (2024) that carried out a study on generative AI in academic research: a descriptive study on awareness, gender usage and views among pre-service teachers and empirically established that male pre-service teachers have higher AI awareness than female pre-service teachers.

Conclusion

Senior secondary school science teachers have Artificial Intelligence tool awareness but hold unfavorable perception about Artificial Intelligence tool. This study is delimited in its scope to specifically investigate the perception and awareness of AI among secondary school science teachers within the public schools of Gashu'a Education zone. The research did not include teachers of non-science subjects or those from other educational zones. The focus was solely on measuring the level of awareness and perceptual attitude towards AI, and not on evaluating practical skills or the school capacity for AI integration.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this study, it was recommended that government should establish workshops to cultivate a favorable perception about artificial intelligence technologies among science teachers.

References

- Alsharidah, M. A. & Alkramiti, A. M. (2024). Teachers' perception towards using AI in Mathematics education. *Amazonia Investiga*, 3 (84), 43-60. <https://doi.org/0.34069/AI/24.84.2.3>
- Asgap, M. S. & Khatima, K., (2024). Exploring teachers' perceptions and implementation of AI in English language teaching. *Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa()*, 825-833.
- Chen, J. & Whitney, D. (209). From perception to consciousness; Searching for the neural foundations of visual awareness, 04(4), 69-637. <https://doi.org/0.06/j.neuron.209.0024>.
- Chen, L., Chen, P. & Lin, Z. (2020). Artificial intelligence in education. *A Review. Volume 8*
doi; 009/Access2020.298850.
- Dewey, J (925). Naturalistic theory of perception by the senses. *The Journal of Philosophy*, 22(22)
- Ezekiel, O.B. & Akinyemi, A.L. (2022). The utilization of artificial intelligence in education: the perception of university of Ibadan lecturers. *Journal of Global Research in Education and Social Sciences*, 6(5).32-40.
- Fakhar, H., Lamrabet, M., Echantoufi, N., Elkhattbi, K. & Ajana, L.n(2024). AI from teachers' perspective and understanding, Moroccan study. *Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 4(6)856-864
- Guneyli, A., Burgul, N.S., Dercioglu, S., Cenkova, N., Becan, S., Simsek, S. E., & Guneral, H. (2024). Exploring teacher's awareness of artificial intelligence in education: a case study from northern Cyprus. *European Journal of*

- Investigating Health psychology*2;4 (8)2358-2376. Doi: 03390/ejihpe408056.
- Haque, M. I. (2024). School teachers' awareness and perception of artificial intelligence in science education: a study of secondary schools. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies* (0), 24-29.
- Hyde, J. S., Bigler, R. S., Joel, D., Tate, C. C., & Van Anders, S. M. (2019). The future of sex and gender in psychology: five challenges to gender binary. *American Psychologist* 72(2), 7-93. <https://doi.org/0.037/amp0000307>
- Kalnina, Nimante, & Baranova, (2024). Artificial intelligence for higher education: benefits and challenges for pre-service teachers. *Front. Edu.* 9:5089.DOI: 03389/feduc.2024.5089.
- Lawal,O.A., Obeten, O. M., Olowookere, A. K., Lagbel, G., Elechi, U. S.,& Enechuwu, E. O. (2025). Assessment and implementation of artificial intelligence tool in Biology teaching and learning at secondary schools in Illorin, Nigeria, *Journal of Pharma Insights and Research*, 03 (02), 2-27. Doi: 0.6963/4z5vh7.
- Ndidi, I. E. Ihechukwu, N.B. Rosekate, U.N. A. Nicholas, N. O. (2024). Assessment of educators' awareness and application of Artificial Intelligence in teacher education. *AJSTME*,0 6) 930-935
- Nyaaba, M., Kyeremeh, P., Majraluwe, E. K., Owusu-fordjour, C.O., Asebiga, E., & A-inkonge, B. (2024). Generative AI in academic research: a descriptive study on awareness , gender usage and views among pre-service teachers. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence*, 8(), 45-60. Doi: 0.6/969/jai.400867.
- Okafor, W. N., & Anyanwu, A. N. (2025). Teachers awareness and utilization of artificial intelligencetool for curriculum implementation in secondary schools in Anambra state. *Journal of Guidance and Counseling Studies* 9 (), 52-6.
- Owan, V. J., Abang, K. B., Idika, D. O., Etta, E. O. & Bassey, B. A. (2023). Exploring the potential of artificial Intelligence tool in educational measurement and assessment. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education.* 9 (8), -5. Do: <https://doi.org/0.29333/ejmste/3428>.
- Owan, V.J. Abang, K. B., Idika, D. O., Etta, E. O. & Bassey, B. A. (2023). Exploring the potential of Artificial intelligence tool in educational measurement and assessment. *Eurasia Journal of mathematics, Science and Technology education*, 9(8), -5. DOI: <https://doi.org/0.29333/ejmste/3428>
- Paie,D. H. (2025). Assessing the use of artificial intelligence in classroom: teachers' perspective. *Journal of Education and Academic Setting* 2(), -8.Doi; 0.62596/c3b8zj70.
- Pandy, P.K. & Angadi, G.R. (2024). Teachers' perception and attitude towards AI in school education: gender perspective. *Poonam Shodh Rochna, A multidisciplinary peer reviewed and Referenced Research Journal* 3 (5).-0.
- Rehman, L.,Riaz, A., Kausar, R., & Akram, Z. (2025). Teachers and technology: assessing AI awareness and adoption in academia. *International Research Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 4(), 27-49.
- Safar A. H. (2024). Awareness of AI and its uses in educationamong general education school teachers in Kuwait,

Kwait niversity, College of education,
Department of curriculumand teaching
methods.

Thomas, G. Gambari, A. I., Yusuf, H. T.,
Abanikanda, M. O.& Daramola, F. O.
(2024). Assessment of lecturers
awareness of artificial intelligence for
education in Nigerian universities.

Educational Technology Quaterly.
<https://doi.org/055056/etq.77>

Uretmen, S. (2024). Turkish EFL teachers'
awareness and perspectives on artificial
intelligence incorporation in to
language instruction. Unpublished
master's thesis Department of foreign
language education, Necmetin Erban
University.